

Studies on Transition Metal Complexes of Heterocyclic Compounds—II

Physico-Chemical Studies of Fe(III) Complex with Indole-2-Carboxylic Acid

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The reaction of Indole-2-Carboxylic Acid (ICA), with Fe(III) have been studied employing conductometric and pH metric titrations. The complex has also been isolated in solid state and characterised on the basis of absorption studies in the infrared, visible and ultraviolet regions of the spectrum. The presence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding has been observed in case of ligand as well as in its complex with Fe(III). The electronic spectra shows the presence of high intensity charge-transfer bands in U.V. regions. The analytical result shows the stoichiometry 1 : 3 (M : L).

The above studies confirm that the ligand is acting as uninegative bidentate molecule. The carboxylic group of ICA dissociates appreciably and anion participates in the complex formation.

EARLIER work on complexing behaviour of ICA relates mainly to studies in solution¹. Previous work² on the studies of solid complexes have been made by the present author.

Materials and Method :

The pH measurements were carried out by Elico pH meter model LI-10 and the conductance measurements by Systronics type 302 SR No. 344 conductivity meter. All the measurements were taken at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$ by keeping the solution in thermostat. The I.R. spectra of the complex and ligand in solid as well as in Chloroform were recorded by Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer model 577. The I.R. of the solid were recorded in KBr phase and of solution using sodium chloride cell. The ultraviolet and visible absorption spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer 202 U.V. Visible Spectrophotometer in the range $200 \mu\text{m}$ - $400 \mu\text{m}$ and $350 \mu\text{m}$ - $750 \mu\text{m}$ respectively.

All the chemicals used in the present investigation are of A. R. grade. ICA are of Flucka made. The sodium dried absolute alcohol was used. The water used, were double distilled.

Preparation and Isolation of the complex :

On adding an alcoholic solution of ICA (100 ml, 0.1M) to an aqueous solution of Ferric Chloride (25 ml, 0.1M) a dark brown solution obtained which

was concentrated on water bath and kept in the refrigerator for a week to get a brown solid compound. This was again washed with water and carbon tetrachloride to remove excess of ICA and metal. Finally the product was recrystallized from alcohol.

Analysis :

The metal complex was analysed for Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Iron. (Found % C=60.80, N=7.33, H=3.85, Fe=10.55, calculated % C=60.45, N=7.83, H=3.36, Fe=10.45). The result corresponds to the molecular formula $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation of the ICA is assumed as follows :

The complex formation takes place as below :

where $\text{L} = \text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N}$.

Conductometric studies :

In the titration of ICA with Ferric Chloride solution, the conductance of the solution goes on increasing till 3 ml of Ferric Chloride (0.01M)

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solution has been added to 9 ml of ligand solution (0.01M). The rise in the conductance is due to liberation of H^+ ion during complex formation according to the above equation. By addition of further Ferric Chloride, the conductance slightly increases and a break in the curve shows the formation of 1 : 3 complex.

In the same way the titration of 10 ml Ferric Chloride (M/50) against ligand solution (M/5) the conductance of the solution goes on decreasing till the 3 ml of the ligand solution is consumed and a clear break in the curve at 1 : 3 ratio (M : L) confirm the stoichiometry 1 : 3 (M : L).

pH Metric Studies :

The titration were carried out with the solution containing metal and ligand in the ratio, 0 : 1, 1 : 0, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 with 0.1M NaOH (50% alcoholic). The curve for 0 : 1 mixture shows the titration of ligand with sodium hydroxide, the inflexion point at one equivalent of alkali shows that there is only one replaceable hydrogen in ligand. The curve for 1 : 0 mixture, it is observed that for complete formation of metal hydroxide three equivalent of alkali are required as shown by titration of metal solution alone. The initial lowering of the pH in the mixed solution containing metal and ligand in ratio 1 : 1 shows the formation of a complex and release of protonic hydrogen. In the titration of the solution containing metal and ligand in the ratio 1 : 1, only one inflexion point is obtained corresponding to three equivalent of alkali. It is assumed that the ligand react with the metal solution to form 1 : 3 complex with release of one equivalent of proton. The release of proton consumes one mole of alkali and two mole of alkali are consumed for precipitating $\frac{2}{3}$ rd of metal chloride as metal hydroxide. In the titration of solution containing 1 : 2 (M : L) ratio there also one inflexion point is observed showing the liberation of two protons which are neutralised by two mole of alkali and one mole of alkali is utilised for precipitating remaining $\frac{1}{3}$ of metal as hydroxide. In the titration of solution containing 1 : 3 (M : L) ratio shows one inflexion point at three equivalent of alkali which are required to neutralise the three protons released during 1 : 3 complex formation. This shows the existence of only one complex containing metal and ligand in the ratio 1 : 3 and a five membered ring structure for the complex is proposed as below (Fig. 1).

Spectral Studies :

(i) *Electronic Spectra* : The ultraviolet and visible spectra of the complex were recorded by dissolving it in absolute alcohol. In visible region the maximum absorbance was obtained at $395 m\mu$. The spectra in U.V. region shows two intense absorption bands at $44444 cm^{-1}$ and $34882 cm^{-1}$. These transitions do not seem to be d-d transition but may be assigned to charge-transfer because of

their high intensity. As the Fe^{+3} can be easily reduced so the charge transfer will be from ligand to metal. The bands around $34882 cm^{-1}$ and $44444 cm^{-1}$ may be assignable to $\pi \rightarrow t_a$ and $\pi \rightarrow e_g$ transitions respectively. The possibility of intraligand transitions may not be ruled out.

Fig. 1

(ii) *Infrared Spectra* : The I. R. studies show that the ligand is acting as a bidentate molecule. The N—H vibration is observed at $3395 cm^{-1}$ in ICA has been found to shifted at lower frequency, $3300 cm^{-1}$ in complex. The lowering of these frequency may be attributed due to formation of nitrogen-metal bond as the drainage of π electron towards metal through the imino group of the pyrrole ring. The characteristic absorption bands for indole ring³ in the ligand molecule which appear at $1615 cm^{-1}$, $1570 cm^{-1}$ and $1445 cm^{-1}$ have also been found shifted at frequencies $1605 cm^{-1}$, $1565 cm^{-1}$ and $1425 cm^{-1}$ in complex. This may also account for the donation of lone pair of electron from the secondary —NH group of the indole ring to the metal.

The lowering in the C—N stretching vibration in complex from $1295 cm^{-1}$ to $1285 cm^{-1}$ also indicate the involvement of —NH group in co-ordinate bond formation.

A sharp absorption peak of —COOH stretching observed at $1700 cm^{-1}$ in the ligand has been shifted at $1680 cm^{-1}$ in the complex, this change accounts for the involvement of Carboxyl group in complex formation. The nature of the peak of —COOH is different from —NH, the previous is very strong, sharp than the broad —NH peak. It can be empha-

sized that $\begin{matrix} O \\ || \\ C-O-M \end{matrix}$ bond may be stronger than N→M bond. The coupled O—H in plane bending H ($1415 cm^{-1}$) and C—O stretching of —COOH ($1203 cm^{-1}$) of parent ligand molecule are also found to be shifted at frequencies $1335 cm^{-1}$ and $1200 cm^{-1}$ respectively in the complex. This may easily be explained on the basis of electron drainage from the oxygen atom in the complex formation.

Chatt and co-workers⁴ have studied the effect of hydrogen bonding on the N—H stretching frequencies. Some other compounds similar to ICA shows intermolecular hydrogen bonding^{5,6} with the involvement of —NH group of pyrrole ring. In the study of the I.R. of the ICA in chloroform at two different concentration, it was observed that the —NH frequency comes at 3450 cm⁻¹ and 3420 cm⁻¹. This is due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding, because of the electrically positive nature of hydrogen at —NH and atom such as oxygen (C=O), which have local concentration of negative charge in ligand. The energy of the interaction is considerably greater than that of Van der Waal forces. Due to the hydrogen bonding in the molecules, the frequencies of corresponding vibration in solid is reduced⁷.

Iron complex of ICA was also studied at concentration 0.01M and 0.02M in chloroform and it was found that the —NH absorption peaks comes at higher frequencies as compared to that of solid and this may be due to relaxation in the interaction force due to hydrogen bonding. The absorption band at 1200 cm⁻¹ in complex does not shows more change in its spectra in chloroform. The C=O stretching vibration in chloroform also found to occur at higher frequency. On the basis of above discussion, polymeric nature of the complex may be proposed.

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